

Synthesis of Some New Diarylsulphides and Diarylsulphones Containing Quinazol-4-One Moiety

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Manuscript received 18 April 1980, revised 23 September 1980, accepted 5 November 1980

4-Amino-4'-nitrodiphenylsulphide and 4-amino-2'-nitrodiphenylsulphide(I) were smoothly condensed with 2-methyl-3, 1-benzoxazin-4-one(II) to produce the corresponding 2-methyl-3-diphenylsulphidoquinazol-4-ones(III). 2-Styryl-3-diphenylsulphidoquinazol-4-ones(IV) were prepared by heating(III) with the appropriate aromatic aldehydes using piperidine as a basic catalyst. Compounds(IV) oxidized easily by H₂O₂/gl. acetic acid mixture to produce the corresponding sulphones(V). The biological activities of some of these compounds were tested.

Of late we have discussed the synthesis of some new diaryl sulphides and diarylsulphones containing different heterocyclic moieties^{1,2,3}. Recently 4-quinazolones and its derivatives have become of increasing importance, being analgesics⁴, anti-malarial⁵, antispasmodics⁶, potential anticonvulsants⁷ and long acting sedatives⁸. The wide spectrum of clinical application of diarylsulphides and diarylsulphones in medicine as antileprotic, bacterial, insecticidal and antitubercular agents is well known^{9,10,11}. It was thought that incorporation of 4-quinazolone moiety into diaryl sulphides and diaryl sulphones might modify their biological activities. Thus 4-amino, 4'-nitrodiphenylsulphide-(Ia) and 4-amino-2'-nitrodiphenylsulphide(Ib) were smoothly condensed with 2-methyl-3, 1-benzoxazine-4-one(II) to produce the corresponding 2-methyl-3-diphenylsulphidoquinazol-4-ones(III). The condensation was achieved, nearly quantitative, by heating the reactants just over its melting points for few minutes with the elimination of water. Generally this condensation took place as reported in literature¹⁴ via the adjoining mechanism as in the following scheme.

2-Styryl-3-diphenylsulphidoquinazol-4-ones(IV) were easily prepared by fusion(III) with the appropriate aromatic aldehydes using piperidine as a basic catalyst for one hour. It must be mentioned that compounds(IV) can also be obtained by an alternative route which involved condensation of 2-styryl-3, 1-(4H)-benzoxazin-4-ones with (I) by the same previous method.

Oxidation of (IV) with H₂O₂ in gl. acetic acid for at least 7 days at room temperature led to the formation of the corresponding sulphones(V) in fairly good yields. It is noteworthy that compounds(V)

can also be obtained by interaction of 4-amino-4'-nitrodiphenylsulphide and 4-amino-2'-nitrodiphenylsulphide with 2-styryl-3, 1-(4H)-benzoxazin-4-ones. Compounds (IV & V) prepared by different routes were identical (m.p., m.m.p.IR). In support for the structure assignment for the unreported quinazolones (IV & V) are its correct analytical data and the investigation of its I.R¹⁵ spectra which showed a strong absorption band in the region 965-985 cm⁻¹ denotes *trans*-olefinic hydrogens, meanwhile, the strong absorption band in the region

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS III AND IV

Compd.	X	X'	Ar	m.p (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (Calcd/Found)(%)			
						C	H	N	S
IIIa ₁	NO ₂	H	—	205	60	64.78	3.85	10.79	8.22
						64.51	3.61	11.10	8.40
IIIb ₁	H	NO ₂	—	169	62	64.78	3.85	10.79	8.22
						64.65	4.04	10.61	8.40
IVa ₁	NO ₂	H	C ₆ H ₅	228	67	70.44	3.98	8.80	6.70
						70.21	4.05	9.15	6.81
IVa ₂	NO ₂	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	265	68	66.14	3.54	8.26	6.29
						66.21	3.21	8.01	6.41
IVa ₃	NO ₂	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂	236	61	68.44	4.56	10.64	6.08
						68.80	4.70	10.41	6.30
IVa ₄	NO ₂	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	245	72	68.63	4.14	8.28	6.31
						68.41	4.30	8.05	6.40
IVa ₅	NO ₂	H	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OH	214	70	68.15	3.85	8.51	6.49
						68.30	3.61	8.15	6.61
IVa ₆	NO ₂	H	Cinnamyl-	219	74	71.57	4.17	8.34	6.36
						71.40	4.45	8.12	6.08
IVb ₁	H	NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	172	73	70.44	3.98	8.80	6.70
						70.59	3.62	8.52	6.52
IVb ₂	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	186	69	66.14	3.54	8.26	6.29
						66.32	3.32	8.50	6.40
IVb ₃	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂	188	68	68.44	4.56	10.64	6.08
						68.12	4.70	10.30	6.20
IVb ₄	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	192	66	68.63	4.14	8.28	6.51
						68.41	4.30	8.40	6.05
IVb ₅	H	NO ₂	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OH	360	75	68.15	3.85	8.51	6.49
						68.40	3.70	8.38	6.12
IV ₆	H	NO ₂	Cinnamyl-	236	72	71.57	4.17	8.54	6.36
						71.41	4.30	8.12	6.40

1600-1610 cm⁻¹ can be reasonably ascribed to the conjugated C=C stretching vibration. Moreover, i.r. data of compounds V show absorption bands at 1135 and 1330 cm⁻¹ assignable to sulphone group. The prepared quinazolones(IV & V) are high-melting crystalline solids, insoluble in water and most organic solvents. The additive property of the exocyclic CH=CH group in (IV & V) is under our further investigations. Some of the hitherto synthesized quinazolones(IV & V) were tested *in vitro* for their biological activities on some bacteria like *Sarcina lutea*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*. Remarkable effects were obtained at concentrations of 1 × 10⁻¹ to 1 × 10⁻⁵ M. The quinazolonyl sulphones(V) showed superior biological activities than the corresponding quinazolonyl sulphides(IV) in all experiments.

Experimental

Completion of the reaction and purity of the compounds prepared were checked by TLC. Melting points are uncorrected. The i.r. spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP200G spectrometer (Y max in cm⁻¹) using KBr water technique.

4'-Nitro-4-aminodiphenylsulphide(Ia), 2'-nitro-4-amino-diphenylsulphide(Ib) and 2, methyl-3, 1-benzoxazin-4-one(II) were prepared according to the methods given in literature^{1,2,4}.

2-Methyl-3-*p*'-nitrodiphenylsulphidoquinazol-4-one and 2-methyl-3-*o*'-nitrodiphenylsulphidoquinazol-4-one(III): A mixture of *p*'-nitro-4-aminodiphenylsulphide(Ia) and/or *o*'-nitro-4-aminodiphenylsulphido(Ib) (0.01 mole) and 2, methyl-3,1-benzoxazine-4-one(II) (0.01 mole) was heated at 155-60° (oil bath) for 30 min. The mixture was cooled, washed with dil HCl and then several times with water. The crude product was filtered, dried and crystallized from the proper solvent.

2-Styryl-3-*p*'-nitrodiphenylsulphido-quinazol-4-ones and 2-styryl-3-*o*'-nitrodiphenylsulphidoquinazol-4-ones(IV):

Compounds(III) (0.01 mole), the appropriate aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mole) and 1-3 drops of dry piperidine were heated together for one hour. The cooled reaction mixture was triturated with small amount of ethanol, filtered and crystallized from the proper solvent (C-F, Table 1).

2-Styryl-3-*p*'-nitrodiphenylsulphono-quinazol-4-ones and 2-styryl-3-*o*'-nitrodiphenylsulphono-quinazol-4-ones(V):

Compound(IV) (0.01 mole) was dissolved in gl. acetic acid (30 ml) and the solution was warmed if required, left to cool, filtered, and 30% hydrogen peroxide (35 ml) added to it. The mixture was kept

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS V

Compd.	X	X'	Ar	m.p. (°C)	Yield %	Analysis (Calcd/Found) (%)			
						C	H	N	S
Va ₁	NO ₂	H	C ₆ H ₅	255	32	66.01 66.92	3.73 3.64	8.25 8.40	6.28 6.01
Va ₂	NO ₂	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	274	38	60.64 60.50	3.24 3.30	10.10 10.30	5.77 5.50
Va ₃	NO ₂	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂	310	42	65.21 65.31	4.34 4.14	10.14 10.21	5.79 5.51
Va ₄	NO ₂	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	294	36	64.56 65.40	3.89 4.01	7.79 7.61	5.93 5.82
Va ₅	NO ₂	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OH	272	35	64.00 64.12	3.61 3.50	8.00 7.80	5.09 5.85
Va ₆	NO ₂	H	Cinnamyl-	284	38	67.28 67.40	3.92 4.02	7.85 8.11	5.98 6.20
Vb ₁	H	NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	214	40	66.01 66.20	3.73 4.02	8.25 8.02	6.28 6.32
Vb ₂	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	275	41	60.64 60.51	3.24 3.40	10.10 10.30	5.77 5.65
Vb ₃	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂	284	38	65.21 65.08	3.34 3.28	10.14 10.28	5.79 6.02
Vb ₄	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	260	36	64.56 64.41	3.89 4.02	7.79 7.62	5.93 6.02
Vb ₅	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OH	276	35	64.00 63.85	3.61 3.50	8.00 8.08	6.09 6.21
Vb ₆	H	NO ₂	Cinnamyl-	310	34	67.28 67.30	3.92 4.15	7.85 8.05	5.98 6.20

at room temperature for 8 days and the deposited crystalline sulphone was collected and purified (C.F., Table 2).

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